

Infected Radicular Cyst With Sinus Tract Formation :A Case Report

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Abstract - The most frequent cystic lesions that affect the jaw are radicular cysts. They make up between 52% and 68% of all cysts that affect the human jaw and are the most prevalent type of jaw cyst. Typically exhibiting no symptoms, they are identified by standard radiologic examinations. When the lesion is circumscribed, traditional nonsurgical root canal therapy is used to treat radicular cysts or, in the case of a significant lesion, surgical procedures such as enucleation, marsupialization, or decompression are few preferred treatment modalities. The effective surgical management of such large infected case of radicular cyst associated with sinus tract formation is presented in this case report.

Keywords -Radicular cyst, enucleation, periapical cystic lesion, marsupialization

Introduction –

Dentists commonly believe that large periapical lesions, particularly those with distinct borders resembling bone cysts on radiographs, have a lower likelihood of healing following root canal treatment.¹ Radicular cysts are inflammatory odontogenic cysts that occur in the tooth-bearing regions of the jaws. These lesions typically involve the apex of the affected tooth and present as well-defined radiolucent areas on radiographs.² A radicular cyst, also referred to as a periapical cyst or root end cyst, is typically linked to permanent teeth and is rarely found in association with deciduous teeth. This type of cyst generally develops due to inflammation of the pulp and periapical tissues of a non-vital tooth.³ Radicular cysts arise from epithelial cell rests of Malassez (ERM), which remain in the periodontal ligament after root formation and have a dormant capacity for proliferation. The radicular cyst can be considered a defensive, hyperplastic, and reactive lesion stimulated by bacterial antigens from necrotic pulp tissue. While approximately 45% of all periapical granulomas (PGs) contain epithelial cells, not all develop into Radicular Cysts. It is estimated that around 20% of chronic periapical lesions with epithelial cells progress to Radicular Cysts.⁴ These inflammatory cysts often go unnoticed because they are typically asymptomatic. They are usually discovered incidentally during routine radiographic examinations, or when an acute exacerbation of the cystic lesion occurs, leading to the development of clinical signs and symptoms.⁵ This article presents the surgical management of one such large infected case of radicular cyst associated with sinus tract formation.

Case Presentation –

A 54-year-old female patient reported to the Department of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery, with chief complaint of pain in the upper right front region of jaw since 10 days. Patient gave no significant past medical and dental history, After which patient was examined.

On extra oral clinic inspection (Figure 1,2,3) no facial asymmetry was noticed, on extra oral palpation lymph nodes were non tender and non palpable.

Figure 1-Left Side
3 - Right side

Intraoral clinical examination revealed a round to oval swelling which was located over gingiva of maxillary right with 13. Swelling was red localized, fluctuant, tract opening at the discharge was seen from

Figure 2 -Extraoral Profile Figure

examination (Figure 4,5) swelling which was located over anterior region in association oedematous in nature, soft, inflamed and tender with sinus punctum. Spontaneous pus the punctum.

Figure 4- Intraoral photograph

Figure 5- Preoperative photograph

Provisional diagnosis -

Given all the clinical features, just like a few normally occurring lesions inside the oral cavity, the provisional diagnosis of acute exacerbation of chronic periapical abscess with 13 with sinus tract formation was made, radicular cysts with 12 and 13 and chronic periapical abscess with 13 were kept in the differential diagnosis.

After which patient was advised for endodontic Electric and thermal pulp vitality testing which showed negative response in 11,12. 11 and 12 were non tender to percussion test while 13 was tender on percussion.

Radiological findings-

OPG was taken (figure 6) which showed unilocular radiolucency with sclerotic borders and there was no cortical expansion. Patient was subjected to CBCT scan for further exploration of the finding, to check for proximity or any involvement of lesion with nasal floor, since lesion was extensive.

Figure 6- Pre operative Diagnostic OPG

CBCT (figure 7,8) showed that the nasal floor was intact and the radiolucency was seen in relation with 11,12 and 13 in sagittal and coronal planes. Based on these, a 3D construction image was plotted. The dimension of the lesion was measured by using measurement scale which was around 12.95*13.42 mm.

Figure 7- CBCT

Figure 8-CBCT

Treatment plan-

The patient was advised for surgical enucleation under local anaesthesia. Treatment plan was formulated and after explaining it to the patient, his informed consent was taken.

Multidisciplinary approach including oral radiology department, oral pathology department, oral surgery department and endodontic department was opted, Intentional root canal opening with 11,12 was done. Pus discharge was seen with 11, 12 after access opening. After determination of working length and biomechanical preparation, calcium hydroxide intracanal medicament was used for one week. Then, in next appointment, obturation was completed.

Patient was prepared for surgery in next visit, patient was advice routine blood investigations and general medical fitness to undergo surgery under local anaesthesia which included surgical enucleation of cyst, apicoectomy and retrograde filling of involved tooth.

Surgical note : Under all aseptic conditions, patient was well painted and draped, post which administration of local anaesthesia was done, a crevicular incision was made in labial region mesial to 14 extending up to 21 with an oblique vertical releasing incision starting from mid-line of 21 up to vestibule. A full thickness mucoperiosteal flap was reflected and a large bony defect with open apex of 11,12 was seen clinically. Complete curettage, along with granulation tissue removal and enucleation of cystic lesion was done and it was sent for histopathological evaluation. Root end of 11,12 was resected and retrograde filling was done with MTA , and flap closure was done with 3-0 silk with interrupted sutures. Post-operative instructions were given to the patient and patient was kept on antibiotics and analgesics for 5days. Currently, the patient is asymptomatic and she is under follow-up since 6 months.

Figure – crevicular with vertical releasing incision

Figure – full thickness mucoperiosteal flap Reflection

Figure – Bony window created

Figure – Enucleation of cyst

Figure – Immediate post operative photograph

Figure –Enucleated Cystic Specimen

Histopathology report -

The histopathology report confirmed the differential diagnosis of an infected radicular cyst.

Histopathological Diagnosis-

The H and E stained sections show epithelium and connective tissue arranged in a cystic configuration. The epithelium is non-keratinized stratified squamous type, showing an area having arcading pattern while at the other it is only one to two cell layers thick. The connective shows many areas of chronic inflammatory cells, predominantly plasma cells and lymphocytes, an area with few mature boney trabeculae is also visible.

The overall features are suggestive of **RADICULAR CYST**.

Outcome and Follow – up –

Postsurgical follow-up after 1 week showed considerable reduction in the size of swelling with prompt healing of surgical site. At 2 months follow-up, no recurrence was observed and orthopantamograph revealed a new bone formation at the site of cystic lesion .

Figure – One week post opt follow-up

Figure – Two months follow up

Figure- Post operative OPG with Root Canal Treated 11 And 12

Discussion –

A cyst is a pathological cavity with a defined wall of connective tissue and an epithelial carpet, filled with liquid, semiliquid or gaseous content. Growth of a cyst is typically slow, centrifugal and infiltrative.⁶ Radicular cysts are more commonly found in the maxilla, with a prevalence of 60% compared to the mandible, and are typically associated with either buccal or palatal enlargement. In this particular case, the cyst was associated with a significant infected sinus tract formation. These cysts grow slowly, often resulting in tooth mobility, root resorption, and displacement. When infected, they can cause pain and swelling, alerting patients to their presence. However, in our case, despite the presence of a large, chronically infected cystic lesion, there was no observed mobility, root resorption, or displacement of the teeth.² The etiopathogenesis of cysts is particularly controversial, with various theories proposed to explain their formation, including epithelial colonization, epithelial cavitation, and micro abscess formation.

The epithelial colonization theory suggests that an epithelized fistulous tract forms from a periapical abscess that has fistulized to the oral cavity. Once this communication closes, the epithelial cells have fully colonized the abscess, leading to the formation of a radicular cyst. According to the epithelial cavitation theory, clusters of epithelial cells form, and those furthest from the nourishing connective tissue lose vascularization, undergoing degeneration and necrosis, thus creating the cyst's central area.

The micro abscess formation theory posits that degeneration of connective tissue leads to cyst development. The formation of a micro abscess within the granuloma nucleus, accompanied by the presence of stimulated epithelial cells, prompts these cells to grow in an effort to line the newly created cavity.⁷

The surgical treatment of apical periodontal cysts typically involves enucleation, with a strong recommendation to preserve the permanent teeth associated with the lesion. However, the preservation of deciduous teeth varies depending on the situation. Other common surgical procedures include marsupialization (Parsch method), enucleation with primary packing, or marsupialization followed by enucleation (Waldron's technique).²

The application of autologous membrane or bone graft after cyst enucleation offers several benefits. Using regenerative materials after surgically removing maxillary cysts stimulates bone regeneration, minimizes the risk of surrounding bone resorption, and enhances the overall healing process post-surgery. Additionally, these steps support soft tissue regeneration and aid in the anatomical reconstruction of the maxillary area, providing functional and aesthetic improvements for the patient.⁸

After a root canal infection is eliminated, periapical inflammation gradually decreases, leading to wound healing in the periapical area. In cases of apical periodontitis with cyst formation, these cysts must regress before the periapical tissues can return to their original structure. Complete regression of radicular cyst can be seen in possible scenarios¹. The regression of apical cysts and the regeneration of bone occur simultaneously. As osteoblasts deposit bone around the apical cyst, apoptosis occurs in the cyst's lining epithelium, causing the cyst to progressively shrink². During the regression of apical cysts, parts of the cyst's epithelium disintegrate due to the apoptosis of local epithelial cells and the degradation of the

basal lamina by metalloproteinases. This process enables a fibrous connective tissue capsule to grow into the lumen of the apical cysts.⁹

Enucleation and marsupialization or decompression are the two primary treatments for odontogenic cysts. Although enucleation can completely remove the lesion in one procedure, decompression—a more conservative approach—has long been regarded as effective for various types of odontogenic cysts. Yoshikowa et al. suggested that reducing the intraluminal pressure in cysts through decompression allows the surrounding tissues, such as bone and periosteum, to restore the original anatomy. The main advantage of decompression for treating radicular cysts is that it is less invasive, thus avoiding injury to the tooth.¹⁰

- References** – 1. Tian FC, Bergeron BE, Kalathingal S, Morris M, Wang XY, Niu LN, Tay FR. Management of large radicular lesions using decompression: A case series and review of the literature. *Journal of endodontics*. 2019 May 1;45(5):651-9.
2. Deshmukh J, Shrivastava R, Bharath KP, Mallikarjuna R. Giant radicular cyst of the maxilla. *Case Reports*. 2014 May 2;2014: bcr2014203678.
3. Anvika Jr D, Amit R, Mihika D, Shreyash B, Samruddhi R. Radicular Cyst Presenting in a Female Child: A Case Report. *Cureus*. 2023;15(9).
4. Osorio NR, Caviedes-Bucheli J, Mosquera-Guevara L, Adames-Martinez JS, Gomez-Pinto D, Jimenez-Jimenez K, Maz HA, Bornacelly-Mendoza S. The paradigm of the inflammatory radicular cyst: biological aspects to be considered. *Eur Endod J*. 2023 Jan;8:20-36.
5. Bane SP, Rathi NV, Thosar NR, Deulkar PV. Surgical enucleation of radicular cyst in endodontically treated primary mandibular molar. *BMJ Case Reports CP*. 2022 Mar 1;15(3):e248376.
6. Torres-Lagares D, Segura Egea JJ, Rodríguez-Caballero A, Llamas Carreras JM, Gutiérrez Pérez JL. Treatment of a large maxillary cyst with marsupialisation, decompression, surgical endodontic therapy and enucleation. *Journal of Canadian Dental Association*, 77, b87-b87.. 2011.
7. Pekiner FN, Borahan O, Ugurlu F, Horasan S, Sener BC, Olgaç V. Clinical and radiological features of a large radicular cyst involving the entire maxillary sinus. *Clinical and Experimental Health Sciences*. 2012;2(1):31.
8. La Rosa GR, Priolo CY, Abiad RS, Romeo VR, Ambu E, Pedullà E. Assessment of bone regeneration after maxillary radicular cyst enucleation with or without bone grafting materials: a retrospective cohort study. *Clinical Oral Investigations*. 2024 Mar 14;28(4):213.
9. Lin LM, Ricucci D, Lin J, Rosenberg PA. Nonsurgical root canal therapy of large cyst-like inflammatory periapical lesions and inflammatory apical cysts. *Journal of endodontics*. 2009 May 1;35(5):607-15.
10. Pei J, Zhao S, Chen H, Wang J. Management of radicular cyst associated with primary teeth using decompression: a retrospective study. *BMC Oral Health*. 2022 Dec 1;22(1):560.